

Flow rate influence on sediment depth estimation using temperature sensors

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Highlights

- Temperature-based systems can be used to estimate sediment depths in sewer pipes.
- Neglecting hydraulic variables barely affected the accuracy of the depth estimations.
- These systems can be applied to monitor sediment build-up in other urban drainage systems.

Introduction

Sediment accumulation in sewers is a major concern in urban drainage systems, as it causes the loss of hydraulic capacity, generates hazardous gases, and increases the risk of blockages (Wu et al., 2023). Sewer maintenance operations are mostly performed based on previous experiences, as there is no methodology to continuously monitor sediment build-up processes. This study uses temperature sensors to continuously monitor the thermal oscillations in liquid and sediment layers to measure heat transfer processes between both media and, thus, estimate the accumulation of bed deposits, similar to Sebok et al. (2017) in river streambeds. Temperature-based systems were also developed for monitoring sediments in urban drainage systems, but without considering flow conditions in sewers (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023a). Wastewater flows introduce convective heat transfer processes at the water-sediment interface. Consequently, the objective of this study was to evaluate the influence of the convective processes on the estimation of sediment depths using systems based solely on temperature measurements. For this purpose, laboratory experiments in an annular flume were performed using different sediment depths, water temperature gradients and flow rates. The main advantages of this facility were the steady flow conditions to simulate heat transfer processes and the room-temperature control system. The results are of high scientific and operational relevance to improve the understanding of sediment build-up processes and maintenance strategies for urban drainage systems.

Methodology

Materials

The annular flume at the University of Sheffield (UK) was used to perform the experimental campaign (Figure 1, left). The flume consisted of a rectangular cross-section 0.20 m wide and 0.48 m high. The side walls and the bottom plate were made of plexiglass and showed a 2.20 m external and 1.80 m internal diameters. In addition, the vertical position of the lid could be manually operated to set the desired water depth in the flume. Both top (lid) and bottom (walls and bottom plate) platforms could be rotated independently and operated using an automatic control system. Finally, the annular flume was placed in a temperature-controlled room, which provided a room temperature stability of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

The experiment design involved the addition of sediment layers at the bottom of the flume and a water layer on top. The sediment bed consisted of a main layer of fine sand, with a top layer of coarse sand and gravel to avoid resuspension of fines and ensure a constant sediment depth during the experiments (no bed forms). In addition, the flume was equipped with a water bath recirculator (Julabo, UK), which was programmed to simulate wastewater temperatures in sewers. For this purpose, field measurements were used as a reference

(Blumensaat et al., 2023). Finally, flow conditions were established by fixing top and bottom rotational velocities. In summary, 18 tests were performed, combining three sediment depths (H_{sed} : 60, 110 and 160 mm), two temperature patterns (ΔT : 3.0 and 5.5 °C) and three flow conditions (bottom velocities: 0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 m/s).

Two daily cycles (48 hours) were simulated for each experiment to minimise the influence of the initial conditions. The objective was to measure the temperature time series in the flume (water and sediment layers) and estimate the sediment depth by analysing the heat transfer processes. For this purpose, 24 PT100 temperature sensors (RS Pro, UK) were installed at three cross-sections. The distribution of sensors covered the temperature measurements of the room, water, and sediment layer (Figure 1, right).

Figure 1. Photo of the annular flume setup (left), and cross-section scheme of the temperature sensor installation (right). Temperature sensors symbolized by white dots were used to estimate the sediment depths (see Results and discussion section).

Methods

A surrogated model, which was developed from the solution of the diffusion heat equation in the sediment layer, was used to estimate sediment depths from the temperature-based system (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023b, under review). This model relates sediment depth estimations to temperature time-series features in the water and sediment layers, sediment thermal properties and heat loss at the bottom boundary. Temperature pattern features measure the attenuation and phase shift between water and sediment bed temperatures. As these patterns follow sinusoidal series, the differences between amplitudes and phases were computed using the fast Fourier transformation (FFT) to assess the attenuation and phase shift, similar to Luce et al. (2013). Likewise, sediment thermal properties and bottom boundary condition should be determined. For this purpose, the thermal properties of the sediment were analyzed in the laboratory (Table 1), while the bottom boundary condition was determined by measuring the room temperature and estimating the convective heat transfer coefficient of the bottom (2.70 W/m²/°C).

Table 1. Thermal conductivity (W/m/°C) and volumetric heat capacity (MJ/m³/°C) of the fine and coarse sand, and gravel. Mean value \pm standard deviation. Measurements were performed under submerged conditions.

Sample	Thermal conductivity [W/m/°C]	Volumetric heat capacity [MJ/m ³ /°C]
Fine sand	1.94 \pm 0.05	2.87 \pm 0.03
Coarse sand	2.21 \pm 0.06	2.94 \pm 0.04
Gravel	1.60 \pm 0.01	3.63 \pm 0.03

Datasets

The surrogate model was developed and validated under no-flow conditions using the data from a previous study, which simulated diffusion conditions in urban drainage sediments (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023c). In addition, the dataset of the experimental campaign performed at the annular flume is under development.

Results and discussion

Figure 2 shows the attenuation and time-shift of the sediment-bed temperature series as a function of sediment depth in comparison to the water temperatures. The greater the sediment depth, the greater the attenuation and phase difference between the water and sediment-bed temperature series. Amplitudes and phases (first harmonic) were calculated from the temperature time series in the water layer and in the sediment bottom and, subsequently, the features (amplitude ratio and the phase difference) could be computed. Harmonic features were used as input of the surrogate model to estimate the sediment depths. The remaining inputs of the surrogate model were the average room temperature, which simulated the field soil temperatures; the effective sediment thermal properties, which were computed from Table 1, and the convective heat transfer coefficient, which was constant and depended on the material at bottom of the flume. Note that no input parameters related to the flow were required to perform the sediment depth estimations with the surrogate model (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Temperature time series in the water layer (blue line) and sediment bottom (brown lines; Hsed: 60, 110 and 160 mm) for temperature pattern 2.

Figure 3. Comparison of the sediment depths estimated with the temperature-based system (boxplots) and the reference measurements (dashed lines) at 60- (left plots), 110- (middle plots), and 160-mm (right plots), considering three bottom velocities (0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 m/s) and two temperature patterns ($\Delta T=3.0$ °C: top plots, and $\Delta T=5.5$ °C: bottom plots). Dotted lines symbolize a ± 10 mm bound.

Small errors were computed between the sediment depth estimations obtained with the temperature-based system and the reference measurements. The overall accuracy of the temperature-based system estimations was ± 7 mm, similar to previous work where no flow conditions were considered (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023, under review). The uncertainty of the sediment depth estimations for small temperature gradients ($\Delta T=3.0$

°C) was greater than for large gradients ($\Delta T=5.5$ °C). Consequently, the larger the daily temperature gradient the more precise estimations could be obtained. Furthermore, the estimation uncertainty was not affected by the sediment depth. The precision was similar for the range of sediment depths tested, i.e., from 60 to 160 mm. However, the precision decreases for larger depths because the attenuation of the temperature series at the sediment bottom is very large (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023).

The sediment depth estimations generally decreased as the flow increased because the convective heat transfer process in the water-sediment interface influences at low depths. However, the differences between the estimations considering the flow conditions did not exceed 10 mm, meaning that the flow rate and, subsequently, the convective term have minimal impact on sediment depth estimations. Therefore, the temperature-based systems are suitable for monitoring sediment build-up in field applications without the need for developing and integrating hydraulic measurements.

Conclusions and future work

The performance of a temperature-based system for estimating sediment depths in sewers was evaluated, considering different flow conditions and temperature daily patterns. The results showed that the convective heat transfer processes at the water-sediment interface could be neglected because they barely influenced the sediment depth estimation. Consequently, the temperature-based systems could be used for monitoring sediment accumulation in sewer systems without requiring the measurement of hydraulic variables, e.g., flow rates or water depths. Nevertheless, other variables, such as the sediment thermal properties, become significant to estimate sediment depths accurately. For this purpose, Dual-Probe Heat-Pulse systems could be implemented to obtain in situ measurements of sediment thermal properties (Regueiro-Picallo et al., 2023b, under review).

Temperature-based systems could be low-cost and easy to implement in sewer systems. Thus, optimal inspection and cleaning strategies could be performed based on observations rather than periodic operations. This would reduce costs and the risk of combined sewer overflows (CSO) during rainfall events caused by sediment accumulation. Monitoring sediment build-up could be also used to develop accurate sediment transport models in sewer systems. This would lead to optimal sewer system designs and inform the development of digital twin models. Future commercial and scientific perspectives include the installation of these systems to optimize the sediment management in sewer systems and other urban drainage infrastructures.

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References

- Luce, C.H., Tonina, D., Gariglio, F., & Applebee, R. (2013). Solutions for the diurnally forced advection-diffusion equation to estimate bulk fluid velocity and diffusivity in streambeds from temperature time series. *Water Resources Research*, 49(1), 488-506.
- Regueiro-Picallo, M., Anta, J., Naves, A., Figueroa, A., & Rieckermann, J. (2023a). Towards urban drainage sediment accumulation monitoring using temperature sensors. *Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology*, 9, 3200-3212.
- Regueiro-Picallo, M., Langeveld, J., Wei, H., Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., & Rieckermann, J. (2023b). Combining a daily temperature pattern analysis and a heat-pulse system to estimate sediment depths in sewer systems. *Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology*, under review
- Regueiro-Picallo, M., Rieckermann, J., Ebi, C., Bloem, S., & Langeveld, J. (2023c). Combining active and passive temperature signals for estimating sediment depths (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8414447>
- Sebok, E., Engesgaard, P., & Duque, C. (2017). Long-term monitoring of streambed sedimentation and scour in a dynamic stream based on streambed temperature time series. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 189(9), 1-15.
- Wu, J., Ma, Y., & Song, S. (2023). Reducing particle accumulation in sewers for mitigation of combined sewer overflow impacts on urban rivers: a critical review of particles in sewer sediments. *Water Science and Technology*, wst2023394.